

Memorandum

RE: *The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.*

29 September 2021

To: The Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

From K.A.

To the Honourable Chairman, the Clerk and all other Members of the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs,

I am grateful for the opportunity to submit this memorandum.

The purpose of this memorandum is to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the *Promotion of Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021*. Elements of this bill are troubling, but I am grateful for the democratic process that we have, allowing us to express our views and hopefully produce better legislation or to restart the process from the beginning.

In this vein, I would like to register my sincere concern about the Bill. I would like to call attention to the false premises in its preamble used to justify its clauses and then highlight problems with clauses 12-16 and 20. I end by insisting that the process be restarted in such a way to include experts and the category of persons enumerated in the bill to ensure an inclusive process of consensus-building that really adheres to the principle of ‘leaving no one behind’.

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Preambular inaccuracies

The narrative of ‘consensus’ but trouble with definitions

The authors of the Bill frame its consultative process as reflective of a consensus in the country:

“...an **overwhelming consensus is established on the position of the nation** in utter rejection of the practices of and advocacy for the LGBTTTQQAAP+ group in conformity with the customary law and tenets of faith and respect for public morality” (pp.3)

However, it is clear that they intentionally excluded the people that they attempt to legislate against, as none of the categories of persons that they have enumerated in this bill was at the table in its initial consultative process.

Furthermore, there are at least 10 Academics who have based their PhDs or have published on the topic of sexual and gender diversity in Ghana. Their work is available in the public domain (Asante 2017; Banks 2013; Blasius 2013; Dankwa 2021; Gore 2018; Gyamerah et al. 2020; Mohammed 2019; O’Mara 2007; 2013; Otu 2016; Otu 2019; Tetey 2010; Tucker 2018) and are part of a wide array of social science disciplines, including anthropology, communication studies, gender studies, history, post-colonial studies, public health, and sociology. The errors in definitions and concepts riddled in the text make it clear that none of them was consulted in the production of this Bill. The fact that the categories enumerated in the Bill are understood as ‘homosexuality and ...its variants’ (pp.2) indicates that the Bill’s authors lack an understanding of the subject at hand. It is alarming that in Ghana, we are at the precipice of passing legislation about practices and identities that the undersigned legislators are not informed about.

LGBTTTQQAAP+ is a collection of categories that attempt to capture all the ranges of sexual orientation, gender identity and expression and sex characteristics (SOGIESC). The ‘+’ symbolically attempts to capture everything that hasn’t been thought of yet, as what is understood about identities and practices change over time and geographies.¹ ‘Lesbian,’ ‘gay,’ ‘bisexual,’ ‘asexual’ and ‘pansexual’ are categories meant to describe **sexual orientation**. ‘Transgender’ and ‘transexual’ describe minoritized **gender identities** and/or **gender expressions**. ‘Intersex’ describes **sex characteristics** that do not neatly fit into the categories ‘male’ or ‘female’. To be intersex is not an anomaly that requires ‘correction.’ The majority of African intersex organizations and associations fight against medical interventions to ‘correct’ them². Those that do not fight against medical interventions insist on waiting until individuals are 18 years of age beforehand, and are able to give informed consent. ‘Queer’ is an ambiguous marker to denote ‘not cisgender’³ or not ‘heteronormative/heterosexual’ and sometimes serves as a shorthand to capture LGBTTTQQAAP+. ‘Ally’ is meant to reflect solidarity for queer communities and ‘questioning’ signifies an openness to one day have diverse sexual experiences, gender identities and expressions of gender. **LGBTTTQQAAP+ is therefore far more complex than simply a ‘variant of homosexuality’.**

¹ There was a time where in the West, pink a colour attributed to boys, and blue was for girls. Folk understandings include the idea that red was the colour of blood and fire, and these were considered masculine elements, and pink was a boy’s version of red.

² See Astrea 2017. <https://www.astraeafoundation.org/stories/public-statement-african-intersex-movement/>

³ Identifying with the sex assigned at birth.

Furthermore, ‘transgender,’ ‘transexual,’ ‘allied,’ ‘intersex,’ and ‘queer’ ‘and ‘questioning’ people can (and many do) **identify as ‘heterosexual,’** because these (aside for ‘queer’) are **not** necessarily categories of **sexual orientations**, but predominantly **gender identities** and **gender expressions, sex characteristics** and **openness**. ‘Asexual’ persons by definition are not interested in sexual relationships, so they cannot possibly be considered a “variant ...of homosexuality”, nor does it make sense to include them in the attempts to supposedly ‘protect’ people from falling victims of LGBTTQQAAP+ sexual activities” (pp.7). Similarly, it is puzzling that asexual people are included in the prohibition of “LGBTTQQAAP+ Propaganda, Advocacy, Support and Other Promotional Activities” (pp.29). Does this mean that abstinence will be listed among the prohibited activities the Bill seeks to sanction? **Will we convict and imprison our religious figures that lead and advocate for celibate lives?** A fundamental problem with the Bill is that it runs on assumptions that are erroneous and lack the understanding to even capture the populations that it tries to discriminate against.

On ‘public safety’ and ‘protection of health’

“Such interference is justified as reasonably necessary for **public safety** or the economic well-being of the country, for **the protection of health or morals** and the prevention of disorder or crime or for the protection of the **rights of freedoms of others**. State regulation of sexual behaviour is founded on the principle that certain sexual expressions ...are **inimical to public health** or public morality” (pp.4-5). Then they cite “2017 report of the Science Research Council, communicated at the 41h National HIV and AIDS Research Conference in Accra, which indicated that about 18.1 % of people living with AIDS (sic) are gays (men sleeping with men) (sic)” (pp.5).

The above section tries to claim that the proposed bill is necessary for the “protection of health” and “public safety”. This is an argument based on a false interpretation of the research used to support it.

First off, the cited study is not about “18.1% of people living with AIDS⁴ (sic) (being) ...gay.” The public health classification ‘men who have sex with men’ (MSM), captures **behavioural patterns**, not the sexual orientation ‘gay’. MSM includes men who identify as gay, bisexual, or heterosexual. The 18.1% figure reflects the proportion of MSM who have been tested and screened for that year’s integrated bio-behavioural surveillance survey (IBBSS) conducted by the Ghana AIDS Commission in collaboration with the Ghana Health Services and local community-based organizations. Data collection is collected by snowball sampling based on the networks of lay and expert health practitioners and grassroots organisers who seek their friends, families, and community members to include in the study. This is because it is impossible to ‘find’ MSM, get them tested and include produce data on them without establishing trust, especially in Ghana where they are stigmatized and vilified by the media, select political and religious leaders, and state authorities. **The size estimate is inherently biased** because the mode of data collection **skews size estimates of MSM to be smaller than they really are**. Since the size estimates are smaller than they really are, **the percentage of MSM in the size estimates living with HIV will be higher than in reality**.

⁴ HIV means Human Immunodeficiency Virus. This is what people can contract. AIDS is acquired immune deficiency syndrome. People cannot catch this. Most people living with HIV do not have AIDS. AIDS is a collection of symptoms people get when sick from HIV, and is what kills people, not HIV.

Secondly, we must not conflate MSM with ‘LGBTQQIAAP+’ because as stated in the earlier section, LGBTQQIAAP+ attempts to capture a diverse array of SOGIESC, and can include heterosexual people. Yes, there may be high infection rates of HIV among MSM, and we must produce inclusive evidence-based policies that help reduce infection rates. But it makes no sense to produce new laws to criminalize MSM, nor to criminalize all diverse expressions of SOGIESC for “**the protection of health**” or “**public safety**”. The same study that the bill cites states that **the majority of people who have HIV in Ghana are women at 65% (Ghana AIDS Commission 2018, 30)**, the near totality of whom were infected by their male sex partners. In the field of HIV/AIDS education and prevention, it is understood that it is the receiving partner who is more susceptible to contracting HIV than the ‘giving’ or ‘penetrating’ partner. To contract HIV, you must have the virus present and a way to put it into the body. **Therefore, in sex, the phallus is a primary vehicle of transmission, not diverse expressions of sexual activities.** This is why it is extremely rare for women who have sex with women to contract the virus. **Following this logic, should we criminalize the use of a phallus in sex?** Should we prohibit women from having sex with men “for the protection of health?” Should we venerate lesbianism because it promotes better epidemiological outcomes in the face of HIV/AIDS? This would be absurd if we push the proposed logic to its extreme. So, it is troubling that this is an element in the preamble to justify passing a bill that conflates MSM with gay, HIV with AIDS, and LGBTQQIAAP+ with homosexuality, on the bad-faith premise of “promot(ing) health and public safety.”

Problems with the contents of the proposed Bill

Clause 20: undermining health and state regulatory bodies by institutionalizing SOCE and GICE

Clause 20 states that a person who is arrested or sentenced under this act and who “makes a voluntarily (sic) request to access an approved medical help or an approved medical treatment, shall be granted access to the approved medical help or approved medical treatment.” In doing so s/he may be granted flexible sentencing (Clause 21). The wording is dubious. The consequential time, mental and financial burden that this bill will impose upon individuals that the authors are targeting calls to question the degree to which requests for ‘approved medical help’ will be voluntary. Furthermore, this bill attempts to modify policies in health independently from Ghana’s national authorities and experts on the subject, circumventing Act 857: Health Professionals Regulatory Bodies Act. Act 857 provides the Allied Health Professions Council with the responsibility to ensure “the highest standards in the practice of allied health professionals” (Parliament of Ghana 2013, Section 2). The bill is likely to attempt to institutionalize sexual orientation change efforts (SOCE) or Gender Identity Change Efforts (GICE)⁵. In doing so, the proposed legislation will flout the authority of the Ghana Psychology Council, whose object under Act 857 is to “secure in the public interest the highest standards in the training and practice of psychology” (Section 115:2). SOCE and GICE **have been widely discredited and deemed harmful** by the American Psychological Association (American Psychological Association 2009), and run counter to the guidelines set out by all of the credible regulatory bodies in the United Kingdom (British Psychological Society et al.

⁵ euphemistically known as ‘conversion therapy’ or ‘reparative therapy’ “The American Psychological Association refers to these practices instead as ‘sexual orientation change efforts (SOCE)’ or ‘gender identity change efforts (GICE)’ to differentiate from evidence-based forms of therapy” (American Psychological Association 2009).

2019). **All of the above authorities heavily inform Ghana’s regulatory bodies in health practices, notably in providing psychosocial services.** In fact, in 2019 the council wrote ethical guidelines that state that psychologists must “ensure the competence of their services,” when it pertains to “understanding of factors associated with ...sexual orientation (and) gender identity” (Ghana Psychology Council 2019 Section 2.01B). Furthermore, the guidelines state that practitioners are not to “engage in unfair discrimination based on ...gender ...gender identity, ...sexual orientation or any basis proscribed in law (Section 3.01). Lastly, to implement these changes independent from the authority of the Allied Health Professional Council will impose a high financial burden onto the state, as it will have to overhaul established norms in psychosocial teaching and practices. **This runs the risk of coming at a high financial cost which runs counter to Article 108 of the Constitution,** which prohibits parliament from introducing bills independent of the President that impose “...a charge on the Consolidated Fund or other public funds of Ghana or the alteration of any such charge otherwise than by reduction”(Republic of Ghana 1996, art.108).

Clauses 12-16

Exacerbating discrimination and negative social outcomes⁶

Though research produced in consort with Ghanaian state institutions are scarce, people with diverse SOGIESC are likely subjected to higher forms of discrimination in the workplace and education. Abundant reports of this have been documented by civil society organizations (Solace Initiative 2019; Solace Brothers 2017; Solace Brothers Foundation 2015; Isaack 2018; Nwosu-Juba and Anglophone West African LBQT Research Collective 2019), and the absence of state-authored data is a symptom of an unwillingness to devote time and resources to testing and verifying/disproving the overwhelming consensus from local and international NGOs on these issues in Ghana. This is evident by the almost celebratory tone of local news stories that report on the expulsion of students (GhanaWeb 2013), the firing of persons (HotFM.com 2021) or physical assaults on the street (Nuamah 2021) based on perceived or imputed SOGIESC. The passage of this bill will doubtlessly exacerbate this trend, ushering in discrimination in the domain of education, employment, health, and housing, compromising the population’s rights guaranteed by the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), and Chapter 5 of Ghana’s Constitution.

Censoring affirming education

Codifying the concept of ‘proper human sexual rights’ into law will do little to promote favourable demographic outcomes. This is a new but core concept in the proposed legislation that, and until recently, has not been unrecognised outside of Ghana.⁷ ‘Proper human sexual rights’ excludes “any material on comprehensive sexuality education or any other variant of comprehensive sexuality education by whatsoever (sic) name called” as well as “any matter pertaining to sexual orientation and gender identity

⁶ A modified excerpt I wrote, which was added to the CDD memorandum submission.

⁷ Invented by the National Coalition for Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values (NCPHSRFV), virtually no record of the formulation “proper human sexual rights” can be found outside of Ghana and prior to NCPHSRFV’s inauguration in 2013 (NCPHSRFV n.d.).

or reproductive sexual rights as defined to include the promotion of LGBTTTQQAAP+ tendencies and behavioural activities or conduct among children, adolescents and youth” (p24). **Clauses 12-16 reframe education, and service provision as ‘propaganda’ and ‘promotion’ respectively.** Clause 13 imposes up to 10 years in prison for disseminating educational materials that “evoke the interest of (a) child in any activity prohibited under this act (i.e., anything aside from ‘proper human sexual rights’) ...or teach (a) ...child to explore any gender or sex other than the binary category of male or female”. This will have deleterious effects on various demographics, especially those who may have neither the cultural nor economic capital to circumvent the educational infrastructure that this bill attempts to diminish. It will affect young people who are trying to understand their SOGIESC in their formative years of development.

According to the Ghana Demographic and Health and Survey (GDHS), 14% of females aged 15-19 had given birth to at least 1 child in 2014 (Britwum et al. 2017; Ghana Statistical Service, Ghana Health Service, and I. C. F. International 2015a). In that same year, 61.8% and 78.2% of sexually active women and men had never tested for HIV/AIDS respectively (Ghana Statistical Service, Ghana Health Service, and I. C. F. International 2015b). This reflects challenges that Ghana faces in delivering adequate sexual health programming to young people, where they feel empowered to prioritize their sexual health, exercise informed risk reduction, and know where to get tested.⁸

Though the Bill’s attempt to curb ally, intersex and asexual ‘behavioural activities or conduct’ in sexual education may be puzzling (pp.24), its attack on civil society organizations is most worrying.

Curbing health service provisions and the democratic legislative process.

Clauses 12-16 also seek to penalize Ghanaians who encourage people who are minoritized based on SOGIESC to exercise their right to be free from discrimination and violence as guaranteed under Chapter 5 of the Constitution. Furthermore, their **attempt to end access to vital health services** provided by state institutions, which work in concert with a litany of CSOs, may spell disaster. At present, the Ghana Health Service and the Ghana AIDS Commission works with various NGOs to mend the gap in service provision, in attempts to reach all persons regardless of SOGIESC. This will most **likely lead to negative epidemiological outcomes especially for people who are discriminated against based on SOGIESC.** The insidious part is that **Clauses 12-16** seek to penalize the promotion of educational, health and legal services **that are meant to address the negative health and social outcomes linked to the stigma, discrimination, and violence that the Bill propagates.**

Finally, **and most importantly**, clauses 12 a and b will **curb the democratic process** by meting out up to 10 years of prison time for “promoting and supporting sympathy (12 a) ...or **a change in public opinion**” towards acts (and identities) that they proscribe. This means that once signed by the President, **it will be illegal to hold campaigns to repeal or amend the law**, cementing it for eternity. **This would be the first law in Ghana that will foreclose any possibility to be amended or repealed.**

⁸ Only 61.1% and 66.9% of women and men respectively, aged 15-19 know where to get tested for HIV (Ghana Statistical Service, Ghana Health Service, and I. C. F. International 2015b)

Summary of points

The Bill's authors, base their arguments on erroneous interpretations of select studies and they are preoccupied with curtailing homosexuality. However, they conflate MSM with 'gay' AIDs with HIV, and homosexuality with LGBTTQQAAP+, demonstrating a **lapse of understanding in key concepts required to apply tenets of the bill coherently**.

The protection of health and public safety is a false pretence for necessitating the Bill, as authors cite inherently biased data that skews size estimates of MSM to be smaller than they really are. This results in skewing the percentage of MSM living with HIV to be higher. If the authors believe that penalizing sexual behaviours and identities is necessary to stem HIV transmissions, then it would make more sense to criminalize the use of a phallus in sex and promote female same-sex sexual relationships. This is because the phallus is a primary vehicle of HIV transmission and the reason for which there are twice as many women who live with HIV (65%) than men. Transmission between two women however is near impossible.

Clause 20 attempts to institutionalize SOCE and GICE as a means to implicate the medical industry in deliberations over sentencing. This undermines the authority of national regulatory bodies mandated by Act 857 and run counter to the ethical guidelines set by the Ghana Psychology Council. Furthermore, it undermines Article 108 of the Constitution as overhauling best practices and training in psychosocial fields to accommodate the bill would come at a high cost to taxpayers.

Clauses 12-16 Will lead to negative social and epidemiological outcomes for people already stigmatized based on SOGIESC. They will likely **face higher discrimination based on health, housing, education, and employment**, which violates the international legal agreements ICESCR, and CRC, as well as **Chapter 5 of the Constitution**. They also seek to penalize the promotion of educational, health and legal services **that are meant to address the negative health and social outcomes linked to the stigma, discrimination, and violence that the Bill propagates**. Finally, if the bill were to be passed into law, by criminalizing 'promoting ...a change in public opinion,' **it will be the first law that is exempt from democratic principles that allow for laws to be renegotiated, amended and appealed in the future**.

Conclusion

In its present form, the bill is **not fit for purpose to become law**, and I respectfully ask the committee not to recommend its passage.

- The bill shows a lack of understanding of the subjects at hand and rests misinterpretation of the research cited to claim its necessity,
- Experts on SOGIESC in Ghana from a wide range of social science disciplines were evidently not present at its initial writing,
- It violates Chapter 5 and Article 108 of the Constitution,
- It undermines the authority of state institutions,
- Once passed, it cannot be challenged, amended, or repealed.
- It exacerbates inequality and spells poorer social and epidemiological outcomes for the most vulnerable groups in Ghanaian society.

If parliamentarians want to produce a bill that truly promotes the well-being of all sectors of society, I recommend the following:

- 1) We should start this process from scratch and make a solid effort to bring experts and stakeholders to the table. Many of them can be found in the bibliography of this memorandum. I have highlighted them.
- 2) Should members of parliament wish to write a new bill, about LGBTTTQQAAP+ persons, then they should invite them at the initial stages of the writing process.

It hardly seems just to attempt to pass legislation about groups of people without consulting them, and then claim that there is a consensus in the country when neither the persons in question nor experts on diverse SOGIESC were consulted. Let's write legislation that includes and benefits everyone, and truly is in spirit with Agenda 2030's 'leave no one behind' as the bill reportedly aspires to do (pp.8).

Yours truly,

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